

PLOT ANALYSIS OF AMERICAN AND UZBEK STORIES

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Abstract. *This article analyzes a comparative lingua-poetic analysis of Abdulla Qahhor’s “Radiant Peaks” and Jack London’s “The Night-Born”, exploring the structural, thematic, and character-driven parallels and divergences between the two narratives. Using comparative literary analysis and plot structure analysis, the article highlights how both authors implement a five-part plot structure – exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, and resolution – to examine themes of identity, resilience, and societal expectation. Special attention is given to the psychological and emotional development of the female protagonists.*

Keywords: *plot, component, lingua-poetic, dynamic development, protagonist.*

INTRODUCTION

Some linguistic and poetic similarities and discrepancies between the stories of American and Uzbek writers have been studied thoroughly. It was found that Abdulla Qahhor’s story “Radiant Peaks” (*Nurli cho‘qqilar*) is lingua-poetically corresponds to Jack London’s story “The Night-Born.” The plot components of Abdulla Qahhor’s “Radiant Peaks” are as follows:

Exposition – Abdulla Qahhor begins “Radiant Peaks” with the disappearance of a girl named Zuhra, a top student in the 9th grade who was respected by the school administration. Zuhra gives her school supplies to her sister Fotima, saying she is going out to pick some tulips.

Denouement – From the beginning of the story, the writer presents a mystery to the reader: where could a sociable and successful girl like Zuhra have disappeared? Her parents, school administration, and the entire village start searching for her. Her parents do not imagine anything bad has happened to their daughter and they continue to hope that “Zuhra has gone off with a well-educated and handsome young man.” While Zuhra attracted attention with her beauty, her sister Fotima was the opposite; the writer describes Fotima as “less attractive.”

Rising Action – The events of “Radiant Peaks” intensify after Zuhra's disappearance. Zuhra’s sister Fotima, as a deuteragonist, takes on a prominent role after the main character. After graduating from school, Fotima begins working at the village farm. Their mother falls ill and passes away. Upon hearing of her mother’s death, Zuhra returns to her parental home; however, shortly after the funeral ceremonies, she leaves the house again.

METHODOLOGY. Comparative Literary Analysis – the article analyzes the narrative structures, character development, and thematic elements of both stories, such as the use of time and space, to understand how the writers convey their messages.

Plot Structure Analysis: The research work studies the plot components in Qahhor’s “Radiant Peaks,” including the exposition, denouement, rising action, climax, and resolution. This method helps to explore the narrative development and how these components align with Jack London's “The Night-Born.”

Character Analysis: A close examination of character development is central to the research. The article focuses on the contrasting characteristics of the two main sisters, Fotima and Zuhra, in “Radiant Peaks,” and compares them to the development of characters like Lucy

and Trefethan, in "The Night-Born." The psychological and emotional changes in these characters are tracked, especially in relation to their surroundings and situations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

Fotima takes care of her father all by herself and immerses herself in work. One day, her boss praises her, acknowledging that she is one of the leading milkmaids. This situation demonstrates the dynamic development of the deuteragonist.

Fotima works tirelessly for her father after the death of her mother, which, in the author's words, shows that "a spark came from the clod." While Zuhra's escape brought disgrace to her parents, Fotima's reputation in the village rises. Even an educated young man named Samijon takes a liking to her. Because Samijon is a well-mannered and thoughtful person, he tells Fotima that they should find Zuhra for the sake of their father.

Climax – The climax of the story "Radiant Peaks" occurs when Zuhra's whereabouts are discovered, and Fotima goes to see her along with her future husband, Samijon. Zuhra was working as a cashier in a beauty salon. Upon seeing her sister, Zuhra feels embarrassed. When Fotima sees that her sister has become thin and hunched, she feels sorry for her and tells her that she has come to deliver the news of her upcoming wedding.

Fotima takes Zuhra's flat key and opens the door, she sees how the house is in a mess, it seems to her no one lives there. Fotima feels ashamed in front of Samijon because of the mess, blushing with embarrassment. However, Samijon, being a noble person, tells Fotima not to be embarrassed and instead insists they should help Zuhra clean the house and support her.

Resolution – Zuhra explains to her sister that she couldn't cope with serving her husband's family and she grew tired of their daily scolding, which led her to leave her husband's home. In the story, the protagonist is portrayed as a person left alone and hopeless.

The story "Radiant Peaks" ends with Zuhra transforming from a beautiful, top-performing girl striving for bright heights into a lonely, hopeless individual.

Studying the principles of linguistic poetics in the stories "The Night-Born" and "Nurli cho'qqilar" ("The Radiant Peaks") is one of the important tasks. Especially, the unity of time and space is a central theme during the lingua-poetic analysis of stories.

The Unity of Time and Space – the plot of the story "The Night-Born" begins in 1898, with the protagonist wandering around Klondike searching for gold and encountering unexpected adventures. The story ends in 1910 when the protagonist narrates the final events of his life. The life of the second main character, Lucy, is depicted in various settings: a) In Golstead, where an Indian tribe lives – this is where the protagonist, Trefethan, first meets Lucy; b) In Juneau, Alaska – where Lucy marries a man who wishes to open a restaurant, and her life ends unhappily. c) In Yukon Island – this location shows a significant change in Lucy's life, as she finds gold while living there alone. Lucy practices medicine among the Indians, gains their trust, and becomes their leader.

The story "The Radiant Peaks" portrays an event that takes place in a common Uzbek family in the 20th century. Most of the events in the story unfold in a village. The change of settings in the story is linked to the psychological changes of the main characters: a) Fotima-Zuhra's house – the formation of two contrasting characters in the form of the two sisters: Fotima, who is described as unattractive and, according to her mother's favor, a "weak, helpless" girl, and Zuhra, whose heart is full of dreams, sharply differing from her sister; b) The Farm – the events of the story begins to develop as Fotima starts working on the farm. Fotima's fate

gradually changes when she works on the farm, transforming from a weak person into a hardworking and diligent girl. c) Zuhra's apartment – the last setting in the story "The Radiant Peaks". After leaving her husband's home, Zuhra lives alone with her daughter, Venera. The writer attempts to portray the fate of a person who lost her desire to live and abandoned alone.

CONCLUSION.

It's crucial to study lingua-poetically American and Uzbek stories. Jack London utilized the type of Five-Structure plot components in his "The Night-Born", while A. Qahhor used this type of plot structure in his "The Radiant Peaks". The protagonists in both stories strived to be happy in their life; Lucy tried to avoid her daily life and she managed to be a successful rich woman in her future in "The Night-Born", whereas Zuhra was not able to be happy as she did not get adjusted to her husband's family in "The Radiant Peaks".

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